

Triglyceride Glucose Index, and Its Modified Indices as Reliable Alternative Markers for Insulin Resistance in Men with Acute Coronary Syndrome

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Abstract:

Introduction: Acute coronary syndrome (ACS) is a major cardiovascular event exacerbated by factors such as obesity and insulin resistance (IR). Triglyceride-Glucose (TyG) index and its modified indices have recently been suggested as useful stand-in indicators for IR. This study investigates the efficiency of TyG index {and modified indices: with body mass index (TyG-BMI), with waist circumference (TyG-WC), with waist-height ratio (TyG-WHtR), triglyceride to HDL-Cholesterol (TG/HDL) index and combination of TyG+TG/HDL index} in predicting IR in ACS patients in South India.

Methods: This prospective cross-sectional study included 139 participants-69 diagnosed with ACS and 70 age-matched healthy controls-conducted at JIPMER, Puducherry, India. Demographic, clinical and biochemical parameters were recorded. IR was assessed using the Homeostasis Model Assessment of IR (HOMA-IR) and TyG index (and its modified indices). Statistical analyses were performed to evaluate differences between groups and correlations using SPSS statistical software.

Results: Both HOMA-IR and HOMA- β showed significant differences between cases and controls, indicating increased IR and β -cell dysfunction in ACS patients ($p < 0.001$). The TyG index and its modified indices were significantly higher in cases than in controls. A significant positive correlation was seen between HOMA-IR and TyG and modified indices. ROC curve analysis demonstrated that the TyG index had the highest predictive value for IR (AUC: 82.0), with high specificity (94.3%) at a cut-off of >3.90 . Other indices, such as TyG-WC (waist circumference) and TyG-WHtR (waist height ratio), also showed significant predictive potential.

Conclusions: TyG and its modified indices, mainly TyG-WC and TyG-WHtR, may serve as alternative markers (either individually or in combination) for assessing IR in clinical settings especially in remote areas with inadequate medical facilities, providing valuable insights for targeted interventions in this high-risk population.

Keywords: TyG index, Insulin Resistance, Acute Coronary syndrome, ROC analysis, Indian population

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Introduction

Acute coronary syndrome (ACS) is an acute cardiac event resulting from acute coronary thrombosis as a product of atherosclerotic coronary heart disease [1,2]. The last century has seen a rapid increase in the global prevalence of cardiovascular diseases (CVD). The Global Burden of Disease study estimate of age-standardised CVD death rate of 272 per 100 000 population in India is higher than the global average of 235 per 100 000 population which makes it the leading cause of mortality in India [3]. Indians are more susceptible to CVD at a higher frequency and at a younger age

compared to other ethnic groups, with South Indians being particularly at greater risk [4]. ACS is commonly caused by the disruption of atherosclerotic plaques in the coronary arteries. Key risk factors include smoking, high blood pressure, diabetes, elevated cholesterol levels, male gender, lack of physical activity, a family history of obesity, and unhealthy dietary patterns [4]. Diabetes is one of the major risk factors for CVDs and up to 37% of patients presenting with ACS suffer from diabetes mellitus (DM) [5,6]. Patients with diabetes who experience ACS face a

persistently elevated risk of recurrent ischemic cardiovascular events compared to those without diabetes, even when managed according to current guideline-recommended treatments [7,8]. Insulin resistance (IR) is linked to ACS and serves as a significant predictor of adverse outcomes in patients hospitalized with myocardial infarction (MI) [9,10]. Accurately quantifying IR has long been a challenge. The traditional gold standard, the hyper-insulinemic-euglycemic clamp technique, is both expensive and technically complex, making it difficult to apply in large-scale cohort studies [11].

To address these challenges, the homeostasis model assessment for insulin resistance (HOMA-IR) was introduced in 1985 and has since been widely utilized for quantifying insulin resistance. Precise measurement of HOMA-IR requires the use of fasting insulin and glucose concentrations [12] which is difficult to assess in patients of ACS at the time of presentation to the emergency services [10]. Previous studies have reported alternative markers like Admission insulin resistance index (AIRI) which were found to be as effective as HOMA-IR in detecting IR with simpler methodology without the requirement of a fasting blood sample [10,13]. But even this method required the estimation of serum insulin which is expensive, not properly standardised and is not readily available in many routine laboratories [14]. Additionally, the method faces challenges such as high costs and poor reproducibility, which can impact its reliability [11]. Thus, there is need for a simple and inexpensive marker for IR which can be readily assessed even at primary health care centres which usually serve as the point of contact for patients living in rural or remote areas [15].

Identification of quickly accessible and reliable markers could play a crucial role in improving the risk of recurrent CVD risk and predict poor outcome in patients admitted with ACS. Recently, the triglyceride glucose (TyG) index has been proposed as practical and straightforward alternatives for assessing IR [16].

In addition to the TyG index, obesity has been linked to IR. Obesity indices such as body mass index (BMI), waist circumference (WC), and waist-to-height ratio (WHtR) are commonly used due to their practical simplicity. Several studies have assessed TyG-modified indices that combine obesity indices with the TyG index, such as TyG-BMI, TyG-WC and TyG-WHtR, and have found that these combined measures are more effective in identifying IR or diabetes than the TyG index alone [17,18].

A recent article found that the TyG index was slightly more effective in predicting metabolic syndrome in female adults compared to male adults. This difference may be attributed to

significant variations in metabolic and physiological characteristics between males and females, such as differences in lipid metabolism, fat distribution, and hormone levels [19,20].

Previous studies have shown that calculation of HOMA-IR does not provide a better surrogate estimate of insulin action, or of its associated dyslipidemia [21]. Whereas, in other studies usage of established lipid indices for estimating insulin resistance like the combination of TyG index and TG/HDL-c index (TyG+TG/HDL-c index) was found to be better predictors of insulin resistance [22].

TyG index and IR have already been associated with cardiovascular mortality, ACS and incident type 2 diabetes [23] in a large prospective cohort study. There is a paucity of studies in the Indian population comparing the TyG index and its modified indices in predicting IR in patients with ACS. This study aims to fill this gap by evaluating the effectiveness, the current study is aimed to explore the effectiveness of the TyG index and its modified parameters in predicting IR in Indians with ACS. Additionally, to avoid the influence of sex-related factors, we planned to focus exclusively on men for this study.

Materials & Methods

This prospective cross-sectional study was conducted at Jawaharlal Institute of Postgraduate Medical Education and Research (JIPMER), Puducherry, following approval from the Institutional Ethics Sub-Committee (Human Studies) (Certificate no. SEC/2011/4/10). All subjects had provided written informed consent before participation, and the study procedure had been verified to adhere to ethical guidelines of the Indian Council of Medical Research Ethical Guidelines for Biomedical Research on Human Participants, 2006.

The study involved 69 male patients with ACS, including those with unstable angina or acute MI, as cases who presented to the Emergency Medical Services of JIPMER; and 70 age-matched, apparently healthy males as controls. The exclusion criteria for both cases and controls included individuals younger than 18 years, those with valvular heart disease, a history of surgery or trauma within the previous month, cardiomyopathy, chronic renal or liver disease, known cases of connective tissue disease or neoplasm, and those with chronic infectious diseases.

Data on each subject, including demographic details, clinical history, and anthropometric measurements weight, height and waist circumference were systematically recorded after obtaining informed consent. Blood sample (5 ml)

was collected in the morning following a 12-hour fasting period. Parameters like glucose and lipid profile were estimated immediately using well-calibrated fully automated clinical chemistry analyser Rx Imola (Randox, UK). Serum glucose was estimated by photometric, enzymatic method using standard kits from Enzopak, Reckon Diagnostics, and Vadodara, India. Serum total cholesterol and triacylglycerol were estimated by colorimetric, enzymatic method using standard kits from Genuine Bio system, Chennai, India. Serum HDL cholesterol was estimated by colorimetric, enzymatic method using standard kits from Agappe diagnostics, Cochin, India. Serum was separated and stored at -80°C for further analysis of Insulin levels using Chemiluminescence in the Advia Centaur CP Immunoanalyzer.

Indices related to insulin resistance were calculated using standard formulae: TG/HDL-c index = TG (mg/dL) / HDL-c (mg/dL) [22]; TyG index plus TG/HDL-c = TyG index + TG/HDL-c index [22]; homeostatic model assessment for insulin resistance (HOMA-IR) = fasting glucose (mg/dl) x fasting insulin (IU/mL)/405 [24]; homeostatic model assessment for beta cell function (HOMA-β) = 360 x fasting insulin (IU/mL)/ fasting glucose (mg/dl) - 63 [24]; triglyceride glucose index, (TyG index) = Ln (TG [mg/dL] x glucose [mg/dL]/2) [25]; TyG-BMI = TyG index x BMI [25]; TyG-WC = TyG index x WC [25]; TyG-WHtR = TyG index x WHtR [25].

Anthropometric indices calculated using standard formulae: Body mass index (BMI) = weight (kg) / height (m)²; waist to height ratio (WHtR) = WC (cm) / height (cm) [25].

Results are expressed as mean with SD for normally distributed data and as median with interquartile range for non-normally distributed data. Appropriate parametric (independent students t-test) or non-parametric (Mann-Whitney U test) tests were used to compare the continuous variables between the groups. Correlation analysis (Spearman's) was used for the association of TyG index and its modified indices with indices of insulin resistance (HOMA-IR and HOMA-β). ROC analysis was performed to evaluate the diagnostic performance of the TyG index and modified indices in predicting IR. The area under the curve (AUC) was calculated to assess predictive accuracy, with specific attention to sensitivity and specificity at determined cut-off values. p value <0.05 was considered as significant. All analyses were performed using SPSS software version 22.0.

Result

The results show that the case group had significantly higher WC and WHtR than the control group, with WC values of 88 cm (IQR: 77.5-98.0) in the case group and 78 cm (IQR: 72-80) in the control group (p < 0.001). Similarly, WHtR was significantly higher in the case group (0.533 vs. 0.47, p < 0.001). (Table 1)

Table 1: Comparison of Demographic and Anthropometric parameters between cases and controls

Variable	Study Group		p-value
	Case (n=69) (mean ± SD or median with range)	Control (n=70) (mean ± SD or median with range)	
Age (years)	53.9 ± 10.6	52.5 ± 9.4	0.95
Height (cms)	160 (158-166)	163 (158-168)	0.390
Weight (kg)	60 (57.5-67.50)	23.53 (22.83-25.03)	0.128
BMI (kg/m ²)	24.16 ± 2.72	23.92 ± 1.80	0.55
WC (cms)	88 (77.5-98.0)	78 (72-80)	<0.001**
WHtR	0.533 (0.47-0.60)	0.47 (0.44-0.500)	<0.001**

Abbreviations: BMI: Body mass index, WC: waist circumference, WHtR: waist to height ratio. Student's t-test was performed for data expressed as mean±SD. Mann-Whitney U test was performed for data expressed as Median (range). ** p<0.001 highly significant difference between the variables.

The case group had elevated FBS levels (130 vs. 81.50 mg/dL) and higher fasting insulin levels (15.78 vs. 9.7 μU/MI) (p < 0.001).

HOMA-IR was significantly higher in the case group, and HOMA-β was lower in case group

indicating greater IR and β-cell dysfunction (p < 0.001). Triglycerides (TAG) and HDL-c levels also showed significant differences, with TAG levels being higher in the case group (152 vs. 118 mg/dL, p = 0.002), and HDL-c levels higher in the case group (32 vs. 29 mg/dL, p = 0.023). (Table 2)

Table 2: Comparison of Baseline Biochemical Parameters between cases and controls

Variable	Study Group		p-value
	Case (n=69) (median with range)	Control (n=70) (median with range)	
FBS (mg/dl)	130 (102-188)	81.50 (75-92)	<0.001**
Fasting Insulin (IU/mL)	15.78 (10.40-25.56)	9.7 (6.2-15.09)	<0.001**
HOMA-IR	5.96 (2.73-10.92)	1.98 (1.17-3.02)	<0.001**
HOMA-β	76.09 (42.0-144.31)	185.37 (110.46-360.67)	<0.001**
TC (mg/dl)	153 (132.5-194)	165 (144-182)	0.431
TAG (mg/dl)	152 (98.5-217)	118 (86-143)	0.002*
HDL-c (mg/dl)	32 (27-37.50)	29 (25.75-34)	0.023*

Abbreviations: FBS: Fasting Blood Sugar; HOMA-IR: Homeostatic Model Assessment of IR; HOMA-β: Homeostatic Model Assessment of β-Cell Function; TC: serum total cholesterol, TAG: serum triacylglycerol, HDL-c: high density lipoprotein cholesterol. Mann-Whitney U test was performed for data expressed as Median (range). ** p<0.001 highly significant difference between variables; *p<0.05 significant difference between variables

Indices related to IR and metabolic risk, such as the TyG-Index, TyG-BMI, TyG-WC, and TyG-WHtR, were significantly higher in the case group compared to the control group (p < 0.001 for each). TG/HDL index and the combination TyG+TG/HDL index were also significantly elevated in the case group (p < 0.05) (Table 03)

Table 3: Comparison of TyG index and modified indices Between Case and Control Groups

Variable	Study Group		p-value
	Case (n=69) (median with range)	Control (n=70) (median with range)	
TyG Index	3.98 (3.74-4.28)	3.67 (3.56-3.75)	<0.001**
TyG BMI	96.57 (85.59-107.69)	87.20 (82.59-92.77)	<0.001**
TyG WC	348.68 (303.05-393.80)	284.74 (265.22-296.20)	<0.001**
TyG WHtR	2.17 (1.87-2.48)	1.73 (1.62-1.82)	<0.001**
TG/HDL Ratio	4.34 (3.33-6.51)	3.78 (2.96-5.18)	0.032*
TyG+TG/HDL	8.54 (7.02-10.65)	7.48 (6.64-9.07)	0.006*

Abbreviations: TyG Index: Triglyceride and Glucose Index; TyG-BMI: Triglyceride and Glucose Index adjusted for Body Mass Index; TyG-WC: Triglyceride and Glucose Index adjusted for Waist Circumference; TyG-WHtR: Triglyceride and Glucose Index adjusted for Waist-to-Height Ratio; TG/HDL Ratio: Triglyceride to High-Density Lipoprotein Cholesterol Ratio; TyG + TG/HDL: Combined Triglyceride and Glucose Index and Triglyceride to HDL Cholesterol Ratio. Mann-Whitney U test was performed for data expressed as Median (range). ** p<0.001 highly significant difference between variables; *p<0.05 significant difference between variables

A significant positive correlation was observed between TyG and its related indices and HOMA-IR, with the TyG Index (r = 0.499) and TyG-WHtR (r = 0.463) showing the highest correlations.

These values indicate a positive association, where increases in these indices are associated with an increase in IR, and all correlations are statistically significant (p < 0.001). In contrast, the TyG and related indices show negative correlation with HOMA-β, reflecting that higher values in these

indices are associated with reduced β-cell function. The TyG-Index (r = -0.398), TyG-BMI (r = -0.201), TyG-WC (r = -0.318) and TyG-WHtR (r = -0.286) have statistically significant negative correlations.

This suggests that as IR worsens, there is a decline in β-cell function. The TG/HDL index and TyG+TG/HDL index show non-significant correlation with HOMA-β, indicating its limited predictive value (Table 4)

Table 4: Correlation between TyG and its modified Indices and HOMA-IR & HOMA-β (using Spearman's correlation analysis)

Variable	TyG-Index	TyG-BMI	TyG-WC	TyG-WHtR	TG/HDL Ratio	TyG+TG/HDL Ratio
Homa IR Spearman's Rho	0.499	0.421	0.435	0.463	0.180	0.234
p-value	<0.001**	<0.001**	<0.001**	<0.001**	0.034*	0.005*
Homa β Spearman's Rho	-0.398	-0.201	-0.318	-0.286	-0.082	-0.128
p-value	<0.001**	0.018*	<0.001**	<0.001**	0.337	0.134

** p<0.001 highly significant correlation between variables; *p<0.05 significant correlation between variables

ROC Curve analysis was done for TyG index and modified Indices in Predicting Insulin Resistance (Figure 1) (Table 5). Of the above indices, TyG index, TyG-WC and TyG-WHtR demonstrated good sensitivity (>57%) and specificity (>94%) as predictors of IR in patients with ACS. The optimum critical concentration of these indices for detection of IR in patients with ACS were >3.90, >314.82 and >1.95 respectively. Even TyG-BMI

(cut-off of >98.45) could be used a predictor of IR as it showed good specificity (92.9%) but sensitivity (47.8%) was lower when compared to the TyG index, TyG-WC and TyG-WHtR. TG/HDL index and the combination TyG+TG/HDL index showed poorer sensitivity and specificity than the other indices as a predictor of IR.

Figure 1: ROC Curve Comparison of TyG and its Related Indices for Predicting IR

Table 5: Areas under the receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curves for each parameter for predicting insulin resistance

Variable	AUC	Sensitivity	Specificity	Cut-off	Overall Model Quality
TyG Index	82.0	58	94.3	>3.90	0.71
TyG BMI	69.9	47.8	92.9	>98.45	0.72
TyG WC	80.7	72.5	94.3	>314.82	0.75
TyG WHtR	79.8	72.5	95.7	>1.95	0.61
TG/HDL Ratio	60.6	36.2	82.9	>5.65	0.54
TyG+TG/HDL	63.5	34.8	90.0	>10.11	0.51

Discussion

This is one of the first studies to evaluate the TyG index and its modified parameters in IR diagnosis in the South-Indian population with ACS, specifically in men. The HOMA-IR is a widely used yet simplified index of IR, calculated from FBS and fasting insulin levels. In several studies HOMA-IR, along with HOMA-β, has been proven as a primary surrogate marker for assessing IR, β-cell function, and glucose metabolism, offering valuable insights into metabolic health [12,20,21,24]. A study by Ramachandran et al. identified IR (HOMA-IR) as an independent predictor of ACS [9]. Stubbs et al., had also found that IR correlated to mortality in ACS

patients [10]. Hence, IR plays an important role in the development of ACS and is associated with mortality in these patients and needs to be detected at an early stage. The TyG index is an accessible, and reliable clinical marker that has demonstrated strong performance in estimating IR compared to HOMA-IR [23,26]. Our study agreed with this as TyG index and modified indices like TyG-BMI, TyG-WC, and TyG-WHtR in the ACS group was significantly higher than in the control group. A study by Suleiman. et al., the TyG index, TyG-WC and TyG-BMI showed a significant association with prediabetes [27]. In a study by Lim et al., the performance of TyG index combined with obesity indices like TyG-WC, TyG-BMI, TyG-WHtR was better than TyG index alone and TyG-BMI was

found to be the best marker to predict IR in healthy Koreans [25].

In our study TG/HDL index was also significantly higher in the ACS group compared to the control group, pointing to the relationship between dyslipidaemia and IR. Salazar et al., based on a study conducted on an Argentinian population, suggested that the TG/HDL index is effective for identifying individuals with IR [28]. Additionally, the combined TyG + TG/HDL index measured in the ACS group was higher than in the control group, further supporting the idea that this combination may also be used as a predictor of IR similar to the findings of a study done in South American overweight children and adolescents [22].

Correlation analysis with HOMA-IR revealed a significant positive correlation, particularly with the TyG index and TyG WHtR, suggest that as these indices rise, there is a parallel increase in IR. Locateli et al., also observed a similar result, HOMA-IR had a positive correlation with the TyG-index, TG/ HDL index and the combination of the TyG + TG/HDL index [22]. Selvi et al., also found a positive correlation between TyG index, TyG-BMI, TyG-WC and HOMA-IR in Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus (T2DM) patients, thus making it a simple and inexpensive tool for assessing glycemic control in diabetics [15]. In our study, we found a negative correlation between TyG, its modified indices especially TyG-BMI, TyG-WC and TyG-WHtR and HOMA- β , indicating that higher values are associated with reduced β -cell function [24].

In addition, ROC curve analysis was conducted and it revealed TyG index emerged as the strongest predictor, with an AUC of 82.0, a good sensitivity (58%) and very high specificity (94.3%) at a critical value of >3.90 , suggesting it may serve as a reliable indicator of IR in this population. This was followed by TyG-WC and TyG-WHtR, which showed a comparable AUC with higher sensitivity (72.5%) and specificity ($>94\%$). However, TyG-BMI, TG/HDL index and TyG + TG/HDL index presented with lower AUC, poor sensitivity and specificity limiting their usefulness in clinical setting. In contrast to our findings, a study conducted in South Korea; suggested TyG-BMI, TyG-WHtR and TyG-WC with higher AUC in ROC curve to be stronger predictors of IR in healthy individuals than TyG index [25]. A retrospective study reported that the TyG index had a high predictive value for the incidence of major adverse cardiovascular events (MACE) responsible for high rate of mortality among individuals who have suffered a myocardial infarction (MI) [11].

A review article by Liang et al. further affirmed the utility of TyG index as an important tool in management of coronary artery disease (CAD)

patients as higher values of TyG index was associated with higher risk, more severity of lesions and poor prognosis in those patients [29]. A study by Nehru et al. in South- India reported good sensitivity, specificity, and diagnostic accuracy of the TyG index. A TyG index value of 4.5 or higher was indicative of IR, which is linked to several health issues such as dyslipidaemia, CVD, fatty liver, and undiagnosed diabetes. The study concluded that the TyG index is a simple and cost-effective test that can be performed at any healthcare facility helping in early detection [30]. The overall outcomes in our study highlight that the TyG index itself and, particularly when paired with WC or WHtR, provides a reliable measure for predicting IR in male ACS patients, while TyG-BMI index and combination with TG/HDL index are less effective. These results suggest that TyG modified indices, especially TyG-WC and TyG-WHtR, may be practical tools for clinicians seeking to assess IR and related cardiovascular risks in this population. This was the first study to assess the utility of TyG and its modified indices as markers of IR in South Indian male patients with ACS. This finding will be useful as the risk of developing CAD is very high among Indians and implementation of a surrogate marker like TyG index (which is inexpensive and can easily be assessed even in primary care settings) will be useful in detecting population at risk at an early stage.

However, our study also had some limitations. As this was a cross-sectional study with small sample size, the associations identified are not prospective and generalizable. Even the association of TyG index with prognosis and risk in ACS patients couldn't be determined as we had not done any follow up for adverse cardiac events and other complications. Hence, further studies are required involving a larger patient sample of prospective nature with longitudinal follow-up to validate our results.

Conclusions

The study highlights a significant association between TyG and modified indices especially TyG-WC and TyG-WHtR and IR in male patients with ACS. The TyG-index proved to be a strong predictor of IR, emphasising its clinical relevance in assessing cardiovascular risk in a minimally invasive and inexpensive manner. Incorporating such metabolic indices into routine clinical evaluations at primary health care settings can aid in identifying patients susceptible to adverse cardiovascular events. This can help in decreasing the load of patients suffering from CAD by using appropriate preventive strategies.

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